

JURISPRUDENCE

INTERNATIONAL SANITARY CONFERENCE IN DRESDEN A NEW PERSPECTIVE ON QUARANTINE RESTRICTIONS

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Abstract

The article provides an in-depth analysis of how International Conventions on Sanitation have influenced the development of sanitary-epidemiological legislation. It investigates the impact of these conventions on the regulation of quarantine measures and their effectiveness in combating pandemics and epidemics on a global level. The study is focused on the late 19th and early 20th centuries, a period marked by heightened international efforts to control epidemics. The key terms for this research include International Convention on Sanitation, epidemic, and quarantine measures.

Keywords: International Convention on Sanitation, epidemics, quarantine measures.

Introduction

The unification of different countries in the field of health protection is due to the need for international harmonisation of sanitary surveillance and protection of the territories of states, due to periodic epidemics and pandemics. This was seen during the Middle Ages, when specific measures against epidemics quarantines, infirmaries, etc. began to be applied. The author has chosen the chronological framework of the late XIX - early XX century in the light of the fact that this period was manifested, on the one hand, by a surge of epidemics and, on the other hand, by the development of sanitary legislation through the adoption of International Sanitary Conventions. The low effectiveness of sanitary and anti-epidemic measures implemented at the national level forced us to seek a solution to the problem in the international legal arena, in particular at conferences on health protection.

State of the research. At the same time, there are not many studies on this problem. It should be noted the works of such scientists as S. A. Verkhatsky, N. G. Freiberg, F. Martens, scientists touched upon only some aspects of the activity of conferences, and the texts of the Conventions themselves remained without analysis of the applied quarantine measures and their effectiveness. In this regard, it should be noted that in-depth analyses of these issues have not been conducted.

All conferences should always come down to basic ideas; all governments represented at the conference should regularly inform each other of the progress of the epidemic and of the means used to prevent the spread of the disease and its entry into other regions. To begin with, the terrain was classified according to such criteria as: (a.) Suspected of being infected with cholera; (b.) Infected with cholera; (c.) Free from cholera. Outbreak in Hamburg. strong restrictions like military cordons and isolation like 60 years before.

The Austro-Hungarian Government has proposed that representatives from European governments convene at a conference to discuss measures for preventing the spread of epidemics in Europe. They have also sub-

mitted a draft of the proposed agenda for the conference. After receiving agreement from the invited powers, the Austro-Hungarian Government has suggested that the conference take place in Dresden in March of this year. In accordance with these instructions, I am honoured to invite Her Majesty's Government to send representatives to the conference in Dresden on March 11th, and to instruct them to meet with representatives from other powers. [2, p. 66].

The serious interference with international trade and the inconvenience suffered by tourists as a result of the strict measures taken during the 1892 epidemic. In the text of the convention, countries were seeking ways to ease restrictions without negatively impacting economic development, as trade was deemed crucial.

How can the territorial scope of preventive measures against cholera be restricted to exclude anything that is completely harmless?

The text outlines the regulations for trade, specifically which items are allowed to be imported and which are prohibited. The details of these regulations are specified in the paragraphs of the convention. For example, paragraph 4 addresses the prohibition of articles in connection with railways and parcel posts to prevent the spread of cholera. Paragraphs 5-10 cover various conditions and restrictions related to the importation and disinfection of goods [1].

In terms of passenger transport, several questions have been raised. These include: Is it acceptable to impose land quarantines? Under what circumstances can individuals arriving from other countries be prohibited from travelling? When is it appropriate to refuse entry to individuals arriving from abroad? Should passengers be constantly monitored by railway staff? When would it be beneficial for both passengers and train staff to undergo a medical examination during the journey? Can individuals travelling from infected areas be monitored for some time after arriving at their destination? What steps should be taken to ensure that working personnel (such as railway and postal workers) have the right to cross borders for business purposes and, if necessary, stop at locations on the foreign side of borders? Should governments have the authority to implement special

measures against certain groups of people, such as Gypsies and vagrants, or large groups of emigrants and individuals crossing borders? Is it appropriate to leave the regulation of border traffic through special measures to the governments of border regions? [1]

The conference was attended by representatives from Germany, Austria-Hungary, Belgium, Denmark, Spain, France, Great Britain, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, Montenegro, the Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Sweden, Norway, Switzerland, and Turkey [1].

Three committees were set up to discuss the issues that had been raised earlier. The first committee dealt with the duties incumbent on the government in the event of the occurrence of cholera in its country. The second committee dealt with the measures imposed on the government to prevent the spread of cholera into its territory from abroad or from one part of its country to another. These were considered under three headings, namely, measures on land, measures on rivers, and measures at sea. The third committee dealt with traffic on the Sulina Salina at the mouth of the Danube.

Under the Convention, the term "suitable" has a very limited application. It only applies to used clothing and bedding, as well as rags made of chiffon and drill. However, there are some important exceptions for certain types of rags. It was decided that rags shipped in bulk and under the usual conditions for a commodity are not considered suitable and should therefore be free from all restrictions. The same exception was made for clean scraps, similar articles, and woollen articles known as "Kunstwolle" and "shoddy." There was a lot of discussion about these exemptions, not only in the Committee but also in the Subcommittee and in informal meetings that were not recorded. The leading technical delegates, including Professors Koch, Brouardel, and Proust, unanimously agreed that there had been no cases of cholera associated with the exempted rags and that the risk of transmitting cholera through them was so small that the exemptions were justified.

This regulation, as initially presented to the committee, aimed to make it mandatory to disinfect all unwashed linen in the trunks of passengers arriving on a vessel where a case of cholera had occurred within the past seven days. Essentially, it repeated the already mentioned disinfection requirement, and the French delegation strongly advocated for it. The German delegation strongly opposed extending this obligation to arrivals by sea and, after an unsuccessful attempt to persuade the French delegation to modify the proposal, they announced in the committee that they could not accept it. Ships arriving at the Danube from Sulina must adhere to certain general regulations, such as avoiding overcrowding, to maintain a reasonable level of health on board. This plan was presented to the Third Committee and, after some minor amendments were made, it was accepted by the delegates of Russia and Romania. The committee approved its conclusions and recommended them to the full conference, which then unanimously passed them. This was the resolution to what was once thought to be one of the most challenging issues of the "Interrogatory," and its success was largely due to the intervention of scientific experts.

The main conclusions adopted by the Conference and embodied in the Convention were discussed. Some of them involve restrictions which, according to English experience, are necessary or even desirable for the prevention of cholera. However, in terms of land and sea traffic, these regulations are closer to English standards than any previous regulations proposed at international meetings. Some delegations only adopted these conclusions after repeated arguments. It was necessary to constantly point out the negative impact of restrictions, which can give a false sense of security and hinder the adoption of an effective sanitary administration. This is the only sure means of defence against cholera. If the new measures are implemented following the spirit and letter in which they were conceived, significant progress can be made towards freedom of movement and maintaining a higher standard of public health in all represented countries. We hope that this will be achieved. We have taken every opportunity to limit the restrictions that may be imposed on vessels suspected of carrying cholera under the Convention. The current regulations can be seen as defining a maximum and allowing a minimum of restrictions. Even for vessels considered to be infected with cholera, the maximum restriction they may face if they choose to enter a given port is to detain healthy passengers for a maximum of five days from the date of the last case of cholera on board the ship.

As previously mentioned, the Convention offers advantages for unloading goods and aims to alleviate the unfortunate restrictions that have often hindered free trade. This is a significant step towards reducing unnecessary limitations. While some representatives of certain countries have opposed progress, it should be noted that they did so apologetically and expressed hope that their governments would eventually follow the majority of the Powers represented at the Conference. Not once was it suggested that quarantine should be maintained in its stricter form. The Convention, which we are now submitting to your Lordship for consideration, has been signed by the delegates of the following countries: Germany, Austria-Hungary, Belgium, France, Italy, Russia, Switzerland, Luxembourg, Montenegro, and the Netherlands. We are also enclosing a copy of the "Protocol of Signature," which includes the final statements of the various delegations regarding the Convention. This protocol reiterates the previously stated reservation that no "surveillance" of healthy individuals leaving infected ships will go beyond the medical surveillance conducted in their homes in the United Kingdom. No exceptions were made to this provision. Upon reviewing the terms of this document, the objective has been partially achieved [3, p. 42].

Annex 1: Chapter 1 - Measures to inform the governments of the Convention countries of the progress of the cholera epidemic and of the measures taken to prevent its spread and entry into healthy areas: Notification and follow-up communications. It is the responsibility of the government of an infected country to notify other governments of the existence of a cholera outbreak. This is a critical measure that will only be effective if

the government is aware of all cholera cases and potential cases in its territory. It is strongly recommended that doctors be required to notify the government of all cholera cases. The notification should include the location of the outbreak, the date of onset, the number of confirmed cases and the number of deaths. Single cases need not be reported. Notification should be sent to diplomatic or consular offices in the capital of the infected country. If the country is not represented in the capital, notification should be sent directly to foreign governments by telegraph. This initial notification should be followed by regular updates at least once a week to keep governments informed of the progress of the epidemic. These updates should include details on measures being taken to contain the outbreak, such as sanitary and health inspections, isolation, disinfection, and vessel and export protocols. Neighbouring countries can also establish a direct link between their border agencies to share information. Each government should also publish the measures taken to prevent the spread of disease from infected areas. This publication should be immediately brought to the attention of the diplomatic or consular agent of the infected country in the capital. If there is no agent in the capital, the communication should be sent directly to the government of the affected country [1].

Annex 2: Measures to be Taken for Ships Arriving from Contaminated Ports and Sailing Up the Danube Until the town of Sulina is supplied with good drinking water, ships sailing up the river must be maintained in a strictly hygienic condition. Crowding of passengers must be strictly prohibited. I. Measures to be Taken at Sulina Ships entering Romania via the Danube must be detained until a medical visit and disinfection procedures have been carried out. Before proceeding up the Danube, ships arriving at Sulina must undergo one or more thorough medical visits during the day. Each morning, at a designated time, the doctor must ensure the health of all passengers and crew on board before allowing the ship to enter the Danube. The doctor will then issue a sanitary passport or certificate to the captain, which must be presented at subsequent stopping points. A daily medical visit will be conducted. Non-infected ships may only stay in Sulina for a maximum of three days. Any contaminated linen must be disinfected upon arrival. Good quality drinking water will be provided to replace any questionable water on board. Bilge water must also be disinfected. These measures will only be applied to ships arriving from ports with a cholera outbreak. Ships from non-contaminated ports have the option to refuse passengers from contaminated ports in order to avoid these restrictions. The sanitary facilities at Sulina must be improved and equipped with modern disinfection appliances. They must also be complete enough to allow for the isolation of sick passengers and crew from infected ships. II. Measures to be Taken on the Banks of the River Minor sanitary stations will be established along the river banks to allow for the landing of sick passengers. These stations must have access to good drinking water and necessary disinfection equipment. An agreement must be reached

between the Russian and Romanian governments regarding these stations. A doctor must be assigned to each station or important stopping point. A designated isolated room must be prepared at each station. All ships must undergo a medical visit when passing these stations. If there are any sick or suspected sick passengers on board, they must be disembarked and isolated. The remaining passengers must also be disembarked and isolated for five days. The cabins, berths, and any other contaminated areas of the ship, as well as soiled linen, rags, and other items, must be disinfected. The bilge hold must also be treated. Good quality drinking water must be provided to replace any questionable water on board. For ships without any sick or suspected sick passengers, the latrines and bilge hold must be disinfected and good quality drinking water must be provided to replace any questionable water on board. After the medical visit, the captain or head of the crew must be given a certificate detailing the precautions and disinfection measures taken. This certificate must also include the number of passengers and crew on board and must be presented at each station. When the ship enters a new district, it must undergo another medical visit. The government's support would be valuable in strengthening the efforts of those in favour of the successful sanitary system in this country. It would also provide other countries with the assurance that their trade will continue to enjoy the freedom from unnecessary restrictions guaranteed by the Convention.

Conclusion

According to the convention, countries protect themselves from the spread of diseases by implementing measures that prevent the import and export of contagious diseases, while minimizing interference in international trade and transport. The author observes that this approach has led to the transformation and improvement of national legislation, making it more adaptable and up-to-date with the adoption of new norms and conventions. This ensures the preservation of public health and protection against contagious diseases.

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